

An Empirical Study on Factors of Workplace Spirituality and Organisational Outcomes

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Abstract

Workplace Spirituality or Spirituality in the Workplace is a movement that began in the early 1920s. It emerged as a grassroots movement with individuals seeking to live their faith and/or spiritual values in the workplace. Spirituality in the workplace means that employees find nourishment for both the vertical and horizontal dimensions of their spirituality at work. Spirituality in the workplace is about individuals and organisations seeing work as a spiritual path, as an opportunity to grow and to contribute to society in a meaningful way. It is about care, compassion and support of others; about integrity and people being true to themselves and others. It means individuals and organisations attempting to live their values more fully in the work they do. This study has been done with the no-probability convenience sampling of 140 samples with the objectives of analysing the factors of WPS and its relationship and importance in organisational outcome.

Keywords: Workplace Spirituality, Organisational Spirituality, Spiritual Workplace / Organisation

Introduction

It is desirable that employees in any organization should work with not only their minds but also with their hearts (spirit) so that they discover meaning and motive, a kind of accomplishment that means the workplace should be a place for them to express entire selves and be pleased. Workplace spirituality provides a sense of personal wholeness, goal, direction and educator are able to mould students from all age groups to experience a wholesome life filled with self-respect and creativity.

It necessitate the endeavour to discover one's ultimate purpose in life, to build up a well-built link to other colleagues associated with work and to have consistency between one's core beliefs and the values of their institution. Thus, when industries collaborate with meaningful workplace spirituality practices, it would advantage individuals and organizations as well.

The concept of organizational spirituality at workplace has been growing now-a-days and people are looking for their spiritual needs at the workplace. There is a requisite to endorse workplace spirituality for growth and progress of employees' organizational commitment and job satisfaction. In many of today's organizations, people only bring their arms and brains to work, not their souls. The outcome is that organizations do not activate the full creativeness and ability of their employees and employees, in turn, do not achieve in raising themselves as complete individual beings. In tough times, it is usual that employees switch to spirituality for solutions, safety and internal harmony.

Workplace spirituality is not about religion or about getting persons transformed into specific belief system. It does not essentially comprise an association to any specific religious belief, but it is grounded on individual values and philosophy. Workplace spirituality also explained as 'spirit at work' from the organizational outlook. Spirit at work is a term that explains the experience of teachers who are passionate about and energized by their work, discover meaning and motive in their work, sense that they can express their absolute selves, and consider associated to those they work.

Objectives of the Study

This study has been done with the objectives of analysing the various factors of WPS and its importance in organisational outcome.

Hypothesis of the Study

H0: there is no significant association between the Workplace Spirituality factors and Organisational outcomes

Need for the Present Study

Also this would help us to understand the six dimensions of WPS and its importance in organisational outcome and results.

Scope of the Study

This study would help the organisations to understand the various factors or components which are very important in constructing and developing of an organisation.

Review of Literature

Spirituality has been termed as the subjective feelings and thoughts that originate from a quest for the sacred and the word 'sacred' means a divine being or ultimate reality perceived by the individual.

In view point of Mitroff and Denton (1999) expresses spirituality as "The basic feeling of being connected with one's complete self, others and the entire universe". Hence, spirituality is usually observed as some internal element, a belief, value, emotion or attitude that moves person's behavior.

According to Ashmos and Duchon, (2000) proposed "Workplace spirituality can be defined as the recognition that employees have an inner life which nourishes and is nourished by meaningful work taking place in the context of a community". It concerns with teachers who observes themselves as spiritual creatures and whose souls need nourishment through work, feels a sense of motive and meaning in their workplace, and a sense of linkage to one another and with their work circle.

In view point of Howard (2002), "Developing our spiritual selves means expanding our consciousness so that we might see the world free of normal constraints and setting ourselves free to see more clearly thereby enables opportunities to creatively enrich our relationships with others".

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Organizational science studies accept and see organizations as spiritual entities. Employees regard for the satisfaction of their spiritual requirements is so inimitable, to unite with higher self, to turn out to be constructive, to be coherent with other beings, and to understand in what manner they merge into a superior context. They aspire to recognize a sense of reason and meaning at workplace as well as a sense of linkage with other fellows in their work circle.

Krishna Kumar & Neck, (2002) reported “Workplace spirituality represents an attempt to experience spirituality not only in their personal lives but also at work where they spend a large amount of time”. When a place of work is able to generate surroundings that are favorable to teachers, be subjected to harmony in conduct and faith, their ethics, and a sense of motive in their profession, a definite configuration of spiritual orientation will appear.

Giocalone and Jurkiewicz, (2003) reveals “Enabling the expression of human experience at its deepest, most spiritual level may not only reduce stress, conflict, and absenteeism, but also enhance work performance”.

Petchsawang and Duchon (2012) mentions in one of its studies “enhancing spirituality in workplace can be seen as an approach to organizational development by enabling the expression of values such as virtue, corporate citizenship, honesty and integrity.

Workplace Spirituality in Indian Culture and Philosophy

India is one of the very few countries having the longest history of unbroken continuity of culture, traditions and ethos. Management was and is not something new to the Indians. Ancient India was one of the leading countries in the world in trade. Moreover, Buddha, Shankaracharya, Guru Govind Singh, Swami Vivekananda, Swami Sahjananda and other spiritual leaders were great organizers. Our managers should remember this great heritage and base their role as a manager on Indian Philosophy which has its roots in VEDANTA.

Lord Krishna says, “Don’t run away. You must learn to face the situation”. This requires inner courage that comes only when the mind is strong and poised. And equipoise in mind comes only when it has a large vision, a macro vision with clear understanding that he is not a single, solitary individual fighting against the world of plurality (multiplicity) but that he is one with the whole universe, one with Lord who is the cosmic person. When we understand that all individuals are interrelated with each one of us having certain responsibilities and duties to the society, then only our vision becomes macro-vision which is the practical need of the day. VEDANTA helps in developing such vision.

“When disappointment stares me in the face and all along I see not one ray of light, I go back to the Bhagvad Gita, I find a verse here and a verse there and I immediately begin to smile in the midst of overwhelming tragedies – and my life has been full of external tragedies – and if they left no visible, no indelible scar on me, I owe it all to the teachings of Bhagvad Gita”. – Mahatma Gandhi.

It teaches self-control, the three-fold austerity, non-violence, truth, compassion, obedience to the call of duty for the sake of duty and putting up a fight against unrighteousness. . . . To my knowledge, there is no book in the whole range of the world’s literature so high above all as the Bhagvadgeeta which is a treasure house of Dharma not only for Hindus but for all mankind”. – Madan Mohan Malaviya.

“Gita preaches, “Have no personal interest in the event, carry out the duty imposed by the position in life, realize that Isvara, at once, Lord, and Law, is the doer, working out the mighty evolution that ends in Bliss and Peace, be identified with Him by devotion and then perform duty as duty, fighting (the problems) without passion or desire, without anger or hatred” – Dr. Annie Besant.

“The Geeta is one of the clearest and most comprehensive summaries of the perennial philosophy ever to have been done. Hence, it’s enduring value, not only for Indians, but for all mankind The Bhagvadgeeta is perhaps the most systematic spiritual statement of the perennial philosophy”.
– Aldous Huxley.

The moment, the man understands the real nature of his SELF and the world, his attitude towards the world changes completely. The world no more remains for him a place for indulgence. The world is no more a place to go merely for sensuous gratification. The world becomes quite a different thing for a man with such an understanding. It brings a basic change in his behaviour with others.

The whole world for him becomes an altar of worship. His work becomes an offering to the Divine in his SELF. Even wealth, name, power, position everything becomes the part of the world and they have to play roles in his life he will not run after these any more. Such people dedicate their lives for the world and not for themselves.

Research Methodology

Descriptive Research is adopted in this research. Descriptive Research is used to describe characteristics of a population or phenomenon being studied. Non Probability sampling method is used to select the samples. Non Probability sampling is a sampling technique where the samples are gathered in a process that does not give at all the individuals in the population equal chances of being selected. Convenience Sampling is a method in which for convenience sake the study units that happen to be available at the time of data collection are selected. With convenience sampling, the samples are selected because they are accessible to the researcher. The sample size of 100 from each region, thus totally 140 samples has been selected for the present study by adopting non-probability convenience sampling.

A questionnaire is a research instrument consisting of a series of questions and other prompts for the purpose of gathering information from respondents. The Workplace Spirituality factors and Organisational outcomes were analysed by using the Chi Square Test.

Dimensions of Workplace Spirituality

Compassion

Lewis & Ebbeck (2014) on their study founded that managers in this study best resonated with the concepts of mindfulness and self-compassion relating them to personal fire experiences that offer

guidance to other managers. From the investigation, and especially through the way participants' described optimal and unfavourable experiences, it became clear that lacking mindfulness and/or self-compassion often led to poor outcomes, distracted thinking, and less effective decision-making. It also became apparent that, as the fire season progresses, managers are prone to being less mindful due to fatigue. Additionally, fire managers have a tendency to internalize failures and can struggle moving past them at times. The methods of using mindfulness and self-compassion that were identified in this research serve as valuable guides for fire managers to enhance their leadership and decision-making capabilities through mindfulness and self-compassion training.

Mindfulness

Langer (1989) has used the term mindfulness to refer to an open and creative attention to one's environment. Mindfulness in this sense allows one to avoid habitual and routine interpretation of stimuli that lead to mindlessness. Instead, stimuli and information are perceived and processed in a more creative and differentiated manner, allowing the creation and refinement of categories, connections, and perspectives.

Spiritual Connection

Kinjerski and Skrypnek (2006) developed the Spirit at Work Scale, an 18 item scale, which focused on the individual experience of spirit at work. The objective of the research was to determine if "spirit at work" was something more than simply their spiritual selves at work. To explore this, the Spirit at Work Scale measured four factors: engaging work; sense of community; spiritual connection; and mystical experience. Their research suggested that spirit at work "is a distinct state that is characterized by cognitive, interpersonal, spiritual and mystical experiences".

Sense of Community

Marques, (2007) pointed out that "an organization that nurtures diversity, flexibility, creativity, and a free flow of communicating, will find its operations improving, and may even grow to become a trendsetter in its industry. When this alignment takes place, a sense of community within the workplace is developed and employees enjoy this sense of community, thus increasing satisfaction. Benefits arise when employees realize that they are now a part of a community".

Meaningful Work

Ashmos and Duchon, (2000) stated that "Spirituality at work is defined as the recognition that employees have an inner life that nourishes and is nourished by meaningful work that takes place in the context of community". Also they have provided the systematic dimensions of Workplace Spirituality: Inner Life, Meaningful Work in terms of meaning and purpose of personal life, and community in terms of connectedness.

Alignment amongst Organizational and Individual Values

Alignment amongst Organizational and Individual Value is an emergent property in organisations that have a critical mass of people with a common language of values and clarity about how their personal values, personal vision/mission and goals align with the desired values, mission/vision and goals of the organisation.

Discussion and Results

Association between Workplace Spirituality factors and Organisational outcomes The association between Workplace Spirituality factors and Organisational outcomes was analysed by employing chi-square test and the results are presented in Table 1.1.

Table 1.1. Association between Workplace Spirituality factors and Organisational outcomes

	Value	df	Sig
Pearson Chi-Square	23.572	8	0.00

Source: Primary Data

The Chi-Square value of 23.572 is significant at one percent level indicating that there is a significant association between Workplace Spirituality factors and Organisational outcomes. Hence the null hypothesis there is no significant association between the Workplace Spirituality factors and Organisational outcomes is rejected.

Conclusion

The six dimensions presented here are the pillars of building a strong spiritual organisation with the committed professionals. This is considering a model of workplace spirituality serve as a partial framework for engaging in a broader conversation of spirituality's place and influence in modern business culture. The recent trend in businesses within our country to reclaim and recognize the spiritual nature of people and the importance of incorporating the "whole person" at work will continue to change the face of how business is done in global scenario for the foreseeable future.

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